

**THE RELATIONSHIP OF SAFETY AND HEALTH MANAGEMENT PRACTICES
ON EMPLOYEES' PERFORMANCE IN MANUFACTURING FIRMS AT PENANG,
MALAYSIA**

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ABSTRACT

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This study evaluated the relationship between welfare management practices, emergency management practices, and safe workplace environment practices on employees' performance in manufacturing firms in Penang, Malaysia. A sample size of 222 respondents was taken from 28 electrical manufacturing firms with a 6322 population and 361 samples to examine the relationship. A questionnaire was designed for data collection to measure welfare management practices, emergency management practices, and safe workplace environment practices on employees' performance in manufacturing firms. A stratified sampling method was used, and the data was analyzed using SmartPls 3.7.8. The study showed that welfare management practices, emergency management practices, and safe workplace environment practices have a significant relationship with employees' performance in manufacturing firms. However, the limitation of this study only covers electrical manufacturing firms. Suggested for future study focus on electronic, plastic, and

fabricated manufacturing firms to be more effective in improving manufacturing firms' safety and health practices.

KEYWORDS: Safety and Health Management, Welfare Management, Emergency management, Safe Workplace Environment, Employees’ Performance

1. Introduction

This research study focuses on the relationship between safety and health management practices on employees’ performance in manufacturing firms in Penang, Malaysia. In this study, safety and health management practices involved welfare, emergency and safe work environment practices. In manufacturing firms, providing a safe workplace environment is an obligation to the task management of each firm. A safe work environment free from any employee safety threats is a priority for every employee (Pilcher & Morris,2020; King,Fortune, Byrne& Brophy,2021) Every employee is free to move around in the workplace environment because the safety and health department provides occupational safety guidelines for any accidents that affect their bodies from disability due to injuries in the workplace. It is the responsibility of each manufacturing firm to complete safety and health management as stipulated under the Occupational Safety and Health Act 1994, which states that each firm must comply with all rules and regulations to ensure that each employee can work safely and their presence in the firms is guaranteed from any accidents and injuries in the workplace. The practice of occupational safety and health management system is an integrated approach to how to manage security and health in the workplace while at the same time ensuring that the improvement of the system operates continuously. The practice of occupational safety and health management system is a set of interrelated elements that interact to establish and implement occupational safety and health policies and their objectives to achieve those objectives to manage risks in the workplace (Callinan, Mojica-Perez, Wright,Livingston, Kuntsche,Laslett,Room& Kuntsche,2021). The use of such systems in the workplace, whether in accredited or non-certified forms, has been proven to minimize the risk to safety and health hazards in the workplace to a minimum. Use of this system is voluntary for any firm, except that the authorities or regulations mandate it through laws, local by-laws or any other similar means.

2. Research Objectives and Research Questions

2.1 Research Objectives

Objectives of the study covered:

1. To identify the relationship between welfare management practices on employees’ performance in manufacturing firms.
2. To examine the relationship between emergency management practices on employees’ performance in manufacturing firms.

3. To evaluate the relationship between safe workplace environment practices on employees’ performance in manufacturing firms.

2.2 Research Questions of the Study

1. Is there any significant relationship between welfare management practices on employees’ performance in manufacturing firms?
2. Is there any significant relationship between emergency management practices on employees’ performance in manufacturing firm?
3. Is there any significant relationship between safe workplace environment practices on employees’ performance in manufacturing firms?

3. Literature Review

3.1 Welfare Management Practices

Previous studies show that there is a significant relationship between welfare management practices on employees' performance in manufacturing firms. Previous research found that many people are unaware of occupational safety and health until an accident, injury, or death occurs. Some employees do not want to invest in safety and health because of cost factors. Even newspapers and electronics do not reveal the importance of safety and health (Vulanovic, Delic, Cosic, Zizakov& Vasic, 2020;Rukuni,Maziriri& Chuchu,2020).When an accident causes injury or death, the tragedy has less place than media coverage. Safety and health management influence the safe behavior of employees at various firms in Malaysia. Safety and health management are among the core indicators of firms' safety outcomes, such as accidents and workplace injuries. Extensive safety and health condition problems are progressively related to increased probabilities of experiencing accidents. The study also stated that lower workplace accident rates are linked to improved safety and healthy work environments (Cahill, Cullen, Anwer, Gaynor& Wilson,2020; Sadiq, 2020). This study's welfare management practices have conceptualized security and health management, which is the performance of employees' work behaviors about the firms' safety, particularly in manufacturing firms. Welfare management practices having been increasingly based on the past studies as the principal variable, asserted two distinct forms of safety and health management covered welfare management practices. Welfare management practices aim to establish a safety-supportive environment with given priority welfare to every employee from any accident, injury, and death. At the same time, welfare management practices aim to ensure that employees work in a manner that adheres to the firms' rules, procedures, and regulations. Therefore, this study has established that welfare management practices play an imperative role in influencing employees' safety performance in terms of welfare management practices (Todorovic, Stajer,Harrison, Korovljevic,Maksimovic & Ostojic,2020;Gornostaj, Mirus& Stanislavchuk,2020).

3.2 Emergency Management Practices

A previous study stated a significant relationship between emergency management practices on employees' performance in manufacturing firms. Emergency management practices included various emergency actions such as establishing an effective emergency response organizational structure to control and curb emergencies, providing emergency procedures to

reduce the impact of injuries, property and environmental damage, ensuring threatened victims are rescued and injured as soon as possible, establish an effective emergency communication system with stakeholders and external emergency agencies, ensure early planning and preparation for emergencies and crises, restore and restore troubles to enable normal operations, preserve information and records for investigation (Faishal, Nuryanti & Masharyono,2019;Atteh Sewu,Gyabeng,Angela Dadzie& Kwame,2019).The study also stated that safety and health management had made the planning and preparations that need to be taken before an emergency occurs, actions that need to be taken during an emergency to contain the crisis and take rescue action and recovery and control work after an accident occurs, including the investigation process. Emphasis on the importance of effective emergency management practices is significant for the excellence of a firm. Various external and internal factors of firms that often change push the firm to be sensitive to environmental threats. In the workplace, the study of employee safety issues involving emergency management practices becomes a severe discussion from time to time. Thus, this study was conducted to identify the level of emergency management practices, the dominant factors that influence employees to neglect safety, and firms' level of preparedness for any accident. This study involves manufacturing firms in the Penang industrial area (Nirtha, Firmansyah& Prahastini,2019;Aruan,Ngurah, Aviantara& Sucipta,2020). To obtain survey data, survey methods using questionnaires were distributed to respondents. The results showed that the emergency management practices at the study location were satisfactory due to the campaigns and activities related to emergency management practices being consistently implemented. Meanwhile, firms' level of preparedness in the face of accidents at work is reasonable because the formulation of safety policies is closely related to the work environment. Extreme negligence was identified as one of the factors that caused workers to neglect safety aspects in the workplace. Therefore, emergency management practices play a role in safeguarding the welfare of employees from any emergencies that occur in the workplace, especially accidents, fires, injuries and deaths (Teuma, Custo, Teuma Custo & Buttigieg,2019;Barron, 2019).

3.3 Safe Workplace Environment Practices

Past studies have found a significant relationship between safe workplace environment practices on employees' performance. Making the workplace safe, healthy and free of accidents and diseases is essential. It will contribute to improving the work environment level, which is one of the vital components of the quality of working life and productivity of firms (Almazrouei, Khalid, Davidson & Abdallah, 2019; Sasmana,2019). This positive effect, in turn, contributed directly to the improvement of the quality of life of workers and the competitiveness of firms in line with the firm's policy goals and transformation plan in the business market. To realize this aspiration, the Department of Occupational Safety and Health (DOSH), a department under the Ministry of Human Resources, is responsible for ensuring workers' safety, health, and welfare in the workplace. Safe work environment practices where each strategy developed in the Master Plan is in line with the direction of firms towards making high-income, technologically sustainable firms in the face of any competition. The goal of the implementation of safe workplace environment practices and

occupational health is to create a safe and healthy work culture among employees by reducing the rate of accidents and occupational diseases, increasing awareness of occupational safety and health and improving the culture of safe workplace environment practices in the workplace with excellent implementation (Bakare& Szmerekovsky,2019;Hoke,Heinzova & Konecny,2019). This can indirectly increase the productivity of firms. Safe work environment practices that are conducive, safe and healthy will make employees healthy, productive and innovative. Directly, this contributes to increased productivity and competitiveness of firms. The rapid development of the country also encourages firms to act proactively and far-sighted to ensure safety and health in the workplace, especially safe workplace environment practices. To achieve this goal, firms have conducted and published studies and reference materials to identify the level of occupational safety and health experience involving safe workplace environment practices by firms and their employees and extend information and guidance to all parties in the firm. In addition, safe workplace environment practices are also enforced through the Occupational Safety and Health Act. Statutory inspections are among the main activities of firms to check that the workplace environment is safe. Safe work environment practices also aim to ensure that the laws enforced are complied with to ensure a safe work environment and machinery and no health risks to workers. Therefore, safe workplace environment practices are essential because of their role in ensuring the safety of the workplace environment is guaranteed and free from any accidents, injuries and deaths that can be avoided (Cheng, Michael,Hamidi& Abdullah,2018;Fischer,Lang,Goetzal,Linnan& Thorpe,2018).

3.4 Employees’ Performance

Employees' performance refers to the quality and productivity of performance in handling their daily tasks given by the organization. To perform a task, employees need a good level of thinking, job knowledge, skills, capability, and desire to improve their work performance to be more professional in performing their daily responsibilities (Martono & Putri, 2018; Sendawula, Nakyejwe Kimuli,Bananuka& Najjemba Muganga,2018;). Recognition of employees creates a positive, productive, and innovative organizational climate in addition to looking at the factors of caring for employee welfare, which is also recognized to affect the employee atmosphere in an organization which is based on various forms of welfare packages created by the organization in producing excellent levels of work performance. The recognition is given, actually encourages more action, and stimulates an employee's thinking to believe that they have the potential and ability to continue to contribute to the progress and success of their organization. Employees' performance through recognition of employees is a form of credit for the quality of work shown by the employees because quality employees are the main assets of an organization (Beltran-Martin & Bou-Llusar, 2018).The quality of work is how a job is executed, and the output from it is the success of meeting the required expectations. If we look at the definition of quality itself is defined as a degree of excellence that is usually high or quality. The quality of work is essential in the management of an organization because, without it, the organization's function, independence, and sustainability can be disrupted (Wang& Guan,2018). Thus, having quality employees at all levels of employment in each department is hope because quality employees translate to the

organization's success in producing first-class human resources, which becomes a valuable asset for organizational excellence in the long run. Every employee feels that their organization pays attention to the importance of giving recognition to their ability to handle their daily tasks because it will directly create a new value for employees in the organization is the value to 'give more' and 'not count' while serving the organization (Lakshmi, Narahari & Koneru, 2018). When employees can produce output as expected, employees' performance is in a state of availability in handling whatever task is directed. Excellent employee performance positively impacts the organization's performance to continue to grow in maximizing profits and wealth (Bernanthos,2018;Soelton,2018).

4. Conceptual Framework

4.1 Independent Variables

- Welfare Management Practices
- Emergency Management Practices
- Safe Workplace Environment Practices

4.2 Dependent Variable

- Employees’ Performance In Manufacturing Firms

4.3 Hypothesis Development

- H1. There is significant relationship between welfare management practices on employees’ performance in manufacturing firms.
- H2. There is significant relationship between emergency management practices on employees’ performance in manufacturing firm.
- H3. There is significant relationship between safe workplace environment practices on employees’ performance in manufacturing firms.

5. Result

5.1 Participants

The data was collected from 28 electrical manufacturing firms, 361 questionnaires were distributed and 222 questionnaires were analysis among the employees. The respondents were selected using the stratified sampling technique.

5.2 Measurement Scale

Questionnaires are designed in Linkert Scale (Strongly Disagree, Disagree, Neutral, Agree, and Strongly Agree).

5.3 Data Analysis

The data obtained were studied using Smart PLS version 3.7.8 to discuss the findings obtained. Smart PLS is highly recommended by statistical scholars in producing accurate analysis of the cause and effect relationship of each variable. Smart PLS is also referred to as a large multivariate analysis technique in social and psychological research. Smart PLS is capable of analyzing measurement model evaluation and structural model evaluation.

Table 1 shown the Loading, Composite Reliability (CR), Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value for each construct studied and the lowest value is 0.5142 and the highest value is 0.5820. These values are greater than 0.5 (> 0.5), confirming that the study construct is able to explain the mean change of variance within the items (Fornell & Larcker, 1981; Gefen & Straub, 2005; Henseler, Ringle & Sinkovics, 2009).

Table 1, Loading, CR & AVE Results

	<i>Loading</i>	<i>CR</i>	<i>AVE</i>
Welfare Management Practices		0.8797	0.5144
WMP1	0.7604		
WMP2	0.7892		
WMP3	0.7720		
WMP4	0.7289		
WMP5	0.7477		
WMP6	0.7265		
WMP7	0.7464		
WMP8	0.7606		
Emergency Management Practices		0.9175	0.5820
EMP1	0.7756		
EMP2	0.7557		

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EMP3	0.7889
EMP4	0.7842
EMP5	0.7672
EMP6	0.7531
EMP7	0.7929
EMP8	0.7812

Safe Workplace Environment Practices	0.9046	0.5427
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SEP1	0.7104
SEP2	0.7949
SEP3	0.7487
SEP4	0.7190
SEP5	0.7324
SEP6	0.7723
SEP7	0.7578
SEP8	0.7545

Employees’ Performance	0.9263	0.5142
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EP1	0.7300
EP2	0.7962
EP3	0.7101
EP4	0.7260
EP5	0.7054
EP6	0.7995
EP7	0.7288
EP8	0.8087
EP9	0.7934
EP10	0.8114
EP11	0.7839

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EP12

0.7653

Figure 1: Structural Model Direct Effects

The discriminate validity test was measured using the Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) criterion test and cross-loading (Henseler et al., 2009). Table 2 below shows the output from the HTMT analysis. The results can be calculated easily using the formula (Henseler, Ringle & Sarstedt, 2015).

Table 2, Discriminate Validity

Constructs	EMP	EP	SEP	WMP
EMP	0.7629			
EP	0.7095	0.7171		
SEP	0.7742	0.7367	0.7367	
WMP	0.7090	0.7469	0.7334	0.7172

Note: Values in Bold face are the square root values of average variance extracted

5.4 Assessment of Structural Model

The findings for testing this direct effect model using Smart PLS software package version 3.7.8 through the structural equation model. This measurement aims to test the direct effect model and the effective model of the mediated variable. Therefore, empirical evidence has been used to construct a direct effect model, as shown in Figure 3.

Table 3, Summary of Hypotheses

<i>Relationship</i>	<i>Summary of Hypotheses</i>				
	beta	Std Error	T-Value	P-Value	Decision
WMP->EP	0.3781	0.06755	0.5546	0.0000	Significant
EMP->EP	0.2332	0.08192	0.7568	0.0000	Significant
SEP ->EP	0.2828	0.07933	0.5375	0.0000	Significant

6. Result

6.1 Welfare Management Practices

The results obtained showed that the welfare management practices variable significantly affects employees’ performance in manufacturing firms ($\beta = 0.3781$; $t = 5.5546$; $p = 0.0000$). H1 Accepted. The results also showed that welfare management practices contributed 38.2% ($R^2 = 0.382$) to employees’ performance in manufacturing firms.

6.2 Emergency Management Practices

The results obtained showed that emergency management practices variable significantly affects employees’ performance in manufacturing firms ($\beta = 0.2332$; $t = 2.7568$; $p = 0.0000$). H2 Accepted. The results also showed that emergency management practices contributed 22.6% ($R^2 = 0.226$) to employees’ performance in manufacturing firms.

6.3 Safe Workplace Environment Practices

The results obtained showed that safe workplace environment practices variable significantly affects employees’ performance in manufacturing firms ($\beta = 0.2828$; $t = 3.5375$; $p = 0.0000$). H3 Accepted. The results also showed that safe workplace environment practices contributed 28.0% ($R^2 = 0.280$) to employees’ performance in manufacturing firms.

7. Discussion

The result showed that there is a significant relationship between welfare management practices on employees’ performance in manufacturing firms. Welfare management practices are the backbone of the social system and development of any manufacturing firms. However, in a country that aspires to be a high -income country, Malaysia seems to have sought to focus on development and expand its social welfare system, apart from cash

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assistance programs. Welfare management practices in Malaysia are highly studied and appreciated, compared to western welfare delivery mechanisms can be said to be declining due to complexity its social structure and arrangement. Based on this background, this study seeks to gain a deeper understanding of the role of manufacturing firms in service welfare management practices from a bureaucratic perspective. Through thematic analysis, the findings reveal that responsible perceptions are prevalent among employees in manufacturing firms. While employees feel strongly that manufacturing firms must be more responsible for welfare management practices while relying on the cooperation of each employee, most manufacturing firms that are closer to employees feel that manufacturing firms, especially in the involvement of all parties are very significant able to manage and organize all their problems. The study concludes that welfare management practices are fully established to foster the role of manufacturing firms in Malaysia.

The result showed that there is a significant relationship between emergency management practices on employees’ performance in manufacturing firms. Emergencies can happen anywhere and anytime. The nature of the emergency is unpredictable and can change in scope and impact. Being prepared and planning ahead is important to protect lives, the environment and property. Emergency management practices plan specifies procedures for handling sudden or unexpected situations. The objective is to be prepared to prevent death and injury, reduce damage to buildings, stocks and equipment, and protect the environment and society. Given that emergencies are imminent, emergency management practices are important. At the onset of an emergency, many decisions have to be made in a short period of time. Time and circumstances can mean the normal chain of command is inaccessible. Moreover, the stress of the incident can result in poor judgment or substantial loss. Developing a program of emergency management practices in advance, training everyone about the program, and reviewing and revising it on an ongoing basis is essential for successful incident management. Instilling confidence in your employees that they know how to respond regardless of the situation is invaluable when minutes are counted. Aside from the obvious benefits of providing emergency management practices, the planning action itself is an important part of the program. The process can identify various deficiencies such as lack of resources (equipment, trained personnel, supplies), or items that can be proactively resolved. In addition, emergency management practices promote safety awareness and demonstrate manufacturing firms' commitment to employee safety.

The result showed that there is a significant relationship between workplace environment practices on employees’ performance in manufacturing firms. Caring for the workplace environment increases productivity, helps retain talent, and most importantly: it’s good for the overall mental health of the company. No jobs are perfect, not even those with great offices, high salaries, or truly vocational tasks. However, whether this condition exists or, more importantly, when it does, there is one thing that can save many situations: taking care of the workplace environment. Workplace environment practices -work atmosphere, in other words- are things you can't see and can't touch, but make you enjoy going to work, feel

comfortable entering the office, don't mind giving yourself some time to work, or recommending people around you to apply for a job at your manufacturing firm. Clearly, in extreme situations, maintaining a work climate is not the most powerful remedy against serious problems a company may face. However, when the situation is not so extreme, a positive workplace environment is one that provides a balance in favor of the company to consider that it has sufficient conditions to provide adequate psychological well-being for the public. On the other hand, when a bad workplace environment, stress and discouragement result, relationships become more tense and less productive, and those who have the opportunity to leave the company will do so as quickly as possible.

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